

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST
DISINTEGRATING TABLETS OF PIROXICAM USING
DIFFERENT SUPER DISINTEGRANTS**

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Abstract:

The scenarios of pharmaceutical drug delivery are expeditiously challenging, but conventional pharmaceutical dosage forms are still dominating. Fast disintegrating dosage forms are those wherein $\geq 85\%$ of labeled amount dissolves within 1 min. Superdisintegrants are used to improve the efficacy of solid dosage forms. The basic approach used in the formulation of the tablet is the use of super disintegrants like SCMC, sodium starch glycolate, and starch 1500, etc. These super disintegrants provide instantaneous disintegration of the tablet after administration in the stomach. Thus, decreasing the disintegration time which in turn enhances drug dissolution rate. The rapid disintegration may be due to the rapid uptake of water from the medium, swelling, burst effect and thereby promoting bioavailability. Tablets formulations are mostly preferred because of the low cost of manufacture, package, shipment, increased stability. For the obtained formulations evaluation studies are carried out. Weight variation, Hardness, Drug content values were found to be within standard limits prescribed. In vitro studies carried out using disintegration apparatus and all the formulations showed release between 70-90%.

Keywords: Piroxicam, Fast disintegrating, super disintegrants, SCMC, starch 1500, sodium starch glycolate, Evaluation studies.

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Please cite this article in press **Afreen Banu et al.**, *Formulation And Evaluation Of Fast Disintegrating Tablets Of Piroxicam Using Different Super Disintegrants...*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Piroxicam belongs to the oxicam family, which is a class of enolic acids structurally unrelated to other NSAIDs. Piroxicam, like other NSAIDs, acts through inhibition of tissue cyclooxygenases (Cox-1 and -2) leading to a decrease in synthesis of pro-inflammatory prostaglandins, which are potent mediators of pain and inflammation. Piroxicam has analgesic as well as antipyretic and anti-inflammatory activities.¹

Piroxicam is used primarily for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis. Other conditions for which it is used include juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis and acute gout. It has been administered for musculoskeletal disorders, minor sports injuries and post-partum pain.²

Figure 1 Structure of piroxicam³

Materials

The preparation of piroxicam tablets involves a variety of ingredients sourced from reputable suppliers. The active pharmaceutical ingredient, piroxicam is supplied by MSN Labs. Excipients such, sodium starch glycolate, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose, acetone sodium, lactose starch 1500, magnesium stearate, mannitol and sodium saccharin are procured from Merk speciality PVT Ltd, India, Mumbai. India The manufacturing process utilizes several key pieces of equipment. An electronic weighing balance from Wensar ensures accurate measurement of ingredients. A Roche Friabilator from lab India, Mumbai, tests tablet friability. Compression of tablets is performed using

a CMD (Cadmach) compression machine. The Pfizer hardness tester from Monosanto.⁴

India measures tablet hardness, while the LAB INDIA UV 3000+ UV spectrophotometer is used for analytical purposes. The Electro lab TDT-08L dissolution apparatus evaluates the dissolution profile of the tablets. Finally, Vernier calipers (model CD-6"CS) are employed for precise measurement of tablet dimensions.⁵

METHODS:**Analytical Method Development**

The absorbance for all the prepared concentrations were scanned in UV Visible spectrophotometer between the wavelengths 200 to 400nm and the λ max was determined as 281nm. Aqueous solubility of piroxicam will be enhanced by preparing solvent deposition system (SDS) by adsorbing it on lactose. SDS of piroxicam was prepared by taking piroxicam: lactose in the ratios of 1: 0, 1:0.5, 1:1 and 1:1.5, 1: 2. Piroxicam solution was prepared in acetone followed by dispersing the known quantity of lactose in it. The resulting dispersion was dried at room temperature. The dried SDS of piroxicam was passed through 60-mesh sieve and subjected for aqueous solubility determination. An excess different ratio of SDS was added in each four test tube containing 5 ml of water and shaking continuously. Then the solutions were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for a minute and the absorbance of the piroxicam test solutions was measured at the characteristic wavelength of 354nm by UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1600).⁶

Preparation Methods of Tablets

Piroxicam tablets were prepared using the direct compression method. Ingredients include acetone, lactose, sodium starch glycolate, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose and starch 1500, magnesium stearate, mannitol and sodium saccharin sodium. Tablets were compressed using 9 mm flat surface punches using 8 station tablet punching machine with the hardness of 4-4.5 kg/cm, each weighing 75 kg/cm².⁷

Table 1 Formulation Composition

INGREDIENTS (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
PIROXICAM	40	40	40	40	40
SODIUM STARCH GLYCOLATE	20	-	-	10	-
SCMC	-	20	-	10	10
STARCH 1500	-	-	20	-	10
MEGNESIUM STEARATE	3	3	3	3	3
MANNITOL	135.5	135.5	135.5	135.5	135.5
SODIUM SACHARRIN	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

Evaluation of Tablets

The formulated Tablets were evaluated for the following quality control studies & In vitro drug r dissolution studies.

Pre formulation studies

Angle of repose

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of response .It is defined as ,the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile ,it slides down the slides of the pile until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of response. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. the angle of response was calculated using the following formula;

$\tan \theta = h/r$ θ =Angle of response

h=Height of the cone ,

r=radius of the cone base.⁸

Table 2 Angle of Repose

Angle of response	Nature of flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk Density (BD) ⁹

Measure the mass of powder and its bulk volume without compaction to calculate bulk density using the formula

Bulk density = M/V₀

Tapped Density ⁹

Measure the mass of powder and its volume after tapping to minimum volume using a tap density tester calculate tapped density using

Tapped density = M/V

Table 3 Compressibility Index limits

CARR'S INDEX	PROPERTIES
5-15	Excellent
12-16	Good
18-21	Fait to possibleA
2-35	Poor
33-38	very poor
>40	very very poor

Post compression Parameters

General Appearance

Evaluate tablets for shape, color, texture, and odor.

Average Weight/Weight Variation ⁹

20 tablets were taken and weighed collectively and individually. From the collective weight, average weight was calculated. Each tablet weight was then compared with average weight to assure whether it was within permissible limits or not. Not more than two of the individual weights deviated from the average weight by more than twice the percentage. The mean and deviation were determined. The percent deviation was calculated using the following formula.

$\% \text{ Deviation} = (\text{individual weight} - \text{Average weight} / \text{average weight}) * 100$

Table 4 Pharmacopoeial Specifications for Tablet Weight Variation

AVERAGE WEIGHT OF TABLET (mg) (I.P)	AVERAGE WEIGHT OF TABLET (mg) (USP)	MAXIMUM PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE ALLOWED
Less than 80	Less than 130	10
80-250	130-324	7.5
More than	More than 324	5

Thickness ⁹

Measure tablet thickness is important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Average thickness for core and coated tablets is calculated and presented with deviation.

Hardness Test ⁹

Measure tablet hardness using a Monsanto hardness tester and the average is calculated and presented with deviation.

Friability Test ⁹

Roche friabilator was used to determine the friability by following procedure .pre weighed tablets were placed in the friabilator. The tablets were rotated at 25rpm for 4 minutes (100 rotations). At the end of test the tablets were re weighed loss in the weight of tablet is the measure of friability and is expressed in percentage as

$\% \text{ Friability} = [(W1 - W2) / W1] \times 100.$

Determination of Drug content

ten randomly selected tablets was weighed and average weight is calculated, the tablets was

powdered in a glass mortar. The weight equivalent to 10 mg of piroxicam is weighed. The weighed amount is dissolved in solvent system in separate 100ml volumetric flask using magnetic stirrer, the volume is adjusted with buffer pH 6.8 in separate volumetric flasks in Lambert's-Beer's range. The drug content in formulation is determined very easily by UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1600) ¹⁰

***In-Vitro* Dispersion Time**

To determine dispersion time 10 ml measuring cylinder was taken in which 6 ml pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ was added and tablet was dropped in it. Time required for complete dispersion was determined. ¹¹

***In-Vitro* Dissolution Study** The development of dissolution methods for RDTs is comparable to the approach taken for conventional tablets, and is practically identical. Dissolution conditions for drugs listed in a pharmacopoeia monograph, is a good place to start with scouting runs for a bioequivalent RDT. Other media such as 0.1N HCl and buffers (pH - 4.5 and 6.8) should be evaluated for ODT much in the same way as their ordinary tablet counter parts. The USP 2 Paddle apparatus has been used for this purpose which is the most suitable and common choice for rapid disintegrating tablets, with a **paddle speed of 50 rpm commonly used. Typically the dissolution of RDT is very fast when using USP monograph conditions; hence slower paddle speeds may be utilized to obtain a profile.** , The USP 1 Basket apparatus may have certain applications but sometimes tablet fragments or disintegrated tablet masses may become trapped on the inside top of the basket at the spindle where little or no effective stirring occurs, yielding irreproducible dissolution profiles ¹¹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The results of absorbance for all the prepared concentrations were scanned in UV Visible spectrophotometer between the wavelengths 354nm and the λ max was determined.

Table 5 Dissolution Parameters

Parameter	Details
Dissolution apparatus	USP -Type II (paddle)
Medium	0.1N HCL
Volume	900 ml
Speed	5000rpm
Temperature	$37 \pm 0.5^\circ \text{C}$
Sample volume withdrawn	5ml
Time points	2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 15, 20 and 30mins
Analytical method	Ultraviolet Visible Spectroscopy
λ_{max}	354nm

Release Kinetics

The release kinetics of the drug from the matrix system were analyzed by fitting the dissolution data to several release models: zero-order, first-order, and diffusion models.

Zero-Order Release:

It defines a linear relationship between the fraction of drug release

$$F = k_0 t$$

F= is the drug release at time, t and k_0 is the zero order release rate constant.

A plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First-Order Release Kinetics: The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\frac{\text{Log}(100-F)}{t} = k$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted then it gives first order release.

Table 6 Observation graph of Piroxicam in 0.1 N HCL (275)

CONCENTRATION (mg/l)	ABSORBANCE
1:1	0.116
1:0.5	0.1848
1:1	0.2583
1:1.5	0.3809
1:2	0.4590

Figure 2 Standard Graph of Piroxicam

Table No 07 : Pre compression studies of Piroxicam

Formulation code	Bulk density	Tapped density	Angle repose	of	Compressability index	Hausner ratio
F1	0.446	0.56	25.74		20.35	1.25
F2	0.48	0.637	25.28		24.6	1.32
F3	0.45	0.55	26.06		18.43	1.22
F4	0.451	0.565	26.65		18.18	1.25
F5	0.462	0.539	27.72		14.46	1.16
F6	0.50	0.625	28.17		20	1.25

Table 8: In-vitro Drug Release profile of various formulation of Piroxicam

Time(min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	00	00	00	00	00	00
5	36.44	26.45	11.25	19.94	16.28	22.17

Table No 09 -: Post compression studies of Piroxicam

Formulation cod	Thickness	Hardness	Friability	Weight variation	Disintegration time	Wetting time	%water absorption ratio	Drug content
F1	4.10	3.0	0.15%	Pass	19 sec	13	119	99.90%
F2	4.41	3.0	0.12%	Pass	23 sec	17	90	99.4%
F3	4.39	3.1	0.48%	Pass	60 sec	22	91	98.24%
F4	4.30	3.2	0.19%	Pass	30 sec	16	84	99.24%
F5	4.31	3.1	0.12%	Pass	38 sec	18	75	99.76%
F6	4.25	3.1	0.55%	Pass	40 sec	15	114	98.72%

Figure 3: *In-vitro* Drug Release profile of various formulation of Piroxicam

Conclusion

This study was carried to formulate and evaluate fast disintegrating tablet dosage form containing Piroxicam a Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug. The present study is an attempt to select best possible combination of diluents and disintegrants to formulate dispersible tablet of Piroxicam which disintegrates within seconds in mouth, thereby reducing the time of onset of action. Lactose is selected as diluents, Sodium starch glycolate, starch 1500, SCMC were used as super disintegrant sodium saccharin was used as sweetening agent to mask bitter taste of Piroxicam.

Quantitative solubility studies showed that Piroxicam is poorly soluble in water. A solvent deposition system was used to increase the solubility of the drug. The aqueous solubility of Piroxicam was enhanced after converting it into Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS). The solubility study indicated an enhancement of aqueous solubility of Piroxicam by solvent deposition on lactose. SDS of Piroxicam prepared with Piroxicam: lactose in the different ratios.

The faster dissolution observed in the case of the solvent deposition system was due to the molecular micronization of the drug particle, which gets coated over the extensive lactose surface. The formulation F1 containing sodium starch glycolate (SSG) with disintegration time 19 sec has shown the highest drug release (99.04%) within 40 minutes than other formulations. This can be attributed to the extent of water uptake and consequently the strong swelling power of this disintegrants caused sufficient hydrodynamic pressure to induce quick disintegration and dissolution of tablet.

On the basis of results obtained from all the evaluation parameters formulation F1 was considered as best formulation among all other formulations

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